

Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus Among Adult Population Within a Southern Nigerian Community

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How to cite this article: Nwafor CE, Edeogu J, Stanley R, Enyichukwu B, Ogomgbunam M. Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus Among Adult Population Within a Southern Nigerian Community. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(1):131-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(1).22

Keywords:

Diabetes mellitus, prevalence, pre-diabetes, Southern Nigeria.

Abstract

Background: The prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) is increasing globally, particularly in low and middle-income countries, driven by factors like rapid population growth, urbanization, obesity, and physical inactivity. In the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria, the pooled prevalence is 9.8%. This study focused on assessing the prevalence of DM in the Rumuomasi community in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. **Method:** 199 persons participated in this cross-sectional study using convenience sampling carried out at an outreach by GoodHeart and Life Support Initiative in November 2023 at the Rumuomasi community in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers state, Nigeria as part of the World Diabetes Day. Fasting blood glucose were collected using two validated glucometers (Kiptrack blood glucose monitor) with a timing of 10 seconds and analyzed descriptively. **Results:** Out of 199 participants (63 males, 136 females), this study found a 6.53% diabetes prevalence (13 individuals), mostly in the 41-60 age group (n=7) and >60 age group (n=5). Despite this, the majority had normal fasting blood glucose. Pre-diabetes was present in 5.53% of the population. **Conclusion:** The prevalence of DM in this community (6.53%) was lower than the earlier reported of 6.8% in Port Harcourt in 2003 and 9.0% in Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. This could be as a result of increasing diabetic – awareness programmes. Enlightenment campaigns on routine glucose checks, campaigns highlighting the value of a traditional lifestyle, particularly with regard to diet should be carried out more often.

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Introduction

According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), (2017) there are approximately 425 million individuals living with diabetes globally, with nearly 50% of them undiagnosed [1]. It is recognized as a significant global health issue and a risk factor for various complications such as blindness, vascular brain diseases, renal failure, and limb amputations, among others [2]. The prevalence of diabetes is on the rise due

to factors like rapid population growth, urbanization, population aging, and the increasing prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity [3]. Complications associated with diabetes include damage to the brain, heart, kidneys, and limbs. Alarmingly, over 50% of individuals living with diabetes are unaware of their condition, particularly in Nigeria where poor healthcare, unhealthy diet, sedentary lifestyle, and poverty persist [4].

Diabetes is a growing problem, especially in low- and middle-income countries. In sub-Saharan Africa, both prediabetes and type 2 diabetes are becoming significant issues. In 2017, the increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes is closely linked to the upsurge in obesity [4]. About 90% of type 2 diabetes is attributable to excess weight. Furthermore, approximately 197 million people worldwide have impaired glucose tolerance, most commonly because of obesity and the associated metabolic syndrome [5]. Over time, diabetes has the potential to cause damage to various parts of the body such as the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys, and nerves. It was predicted that developing countries will bear the majority of the global burden of diabetes epidemics in the 21st century, accounting for 77% of cases [6]. This increase in prevalence could be attributed to factors such as population growth, the consumption of unhealthy foods, obesity, and sedentary lifestyles [7]. The overall pooled prevalence of DM in Nigeria was 5.77% with the pooled prevalence of DM in the south-south zone was 9.8% [8].

According to International Diabetes Federation diabetes is diagnosed through various criteria. These include having a blood glucose level of 7.0mmol/L (126 mg/dL) or higher after an eight-hour fast, or a non-fasting glucose level of 11.1mmol/L (200 mg/dL) or higher along with symptoms of diabetes [9]. It can also be diagnosed if the glucose level is 200 mg/dL or higher on a two-hour glucose tolerance test, or if the hemoglobin A1c level is 6.5% or higher. A fasting blood sugar level less than 100 mg/dL (5.6 mmol/L) is normal. A fasting blood sugar level from 100 to 125 mg/dL (5.6 to 6.9 mmol/L) is considered prediabetes. If it's 126 mg/dL (7 mmol/L) or higher on two separate tests, you have diabetes [10].

It was found that out of a sample size of 199 participants in a study in Dakace village near Zaria, 2% had diabetes and 2.5% had impaired fasting glucose. Only one participant with diabetes had good glycemic control. Among those with diabetes and impaired fasting glucose, some were overweight or obese. Overall, 21.6% of participants were overweight and 7.5% were obese [11].

Diabetes is more common among wealthy and powerful individuals in Africa, earning it the nickname "disease of opulence". It is also more prevalent in urban areas where people are less physically active and consume diets high in saturated fats and refined sugars. Obesity is recognized as a major factor contributing to the increased prevalence of diabetes, leading to the term "diabesity". There is a high prevalence of overweight and obesity worldwide, with over 1.1 billion adults and 155 million children affected. As it turns out, cardiovascular disease is especially common among people with diabetes [5]. Cardiovascular

diseases is a leading cause of death, with diabetes and hypertension as major factors [12] with a prevalence of 6.8% in Port Harcourt [13]. With Port Harcourt being a fast-growing city with and its populace adopting to western lifestyle it is important to know the prevalence of diabetes and pre-diabetes in this city as it provides information on how to improve the health of the people.

This study was carried out to ascertain the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Rumuomasi community in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Its objectives are to determine the age group and gender in which diabetes is more prevalent and the proportion of previously known diabetics in the community.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria Showing the Geopolitical Zones
Source: [14]

Figure 2: Map of Showing the States in South Nigeria
Source: [15]

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out at an outreach done by GoodHeart and Life Support Initiative in November 2023 at the Rumuomasi, a semi-urban community

located in the Obio/Akpor local government of Port Harcourt in River state Nigeria.

199 adults participated in this cross-sectional study using a convenience sampling method. The researchers involved the community and the church leaders to help circulate and informed residents of the outreach/study. Publicity/sensitization was done using church announcements, town hall meeting and town criers for 3 weeks.

Participants were instructed to fast for at least 8 hours before presentation and their fasting blood glucose were estimated. Pregnant women and lactating mothers were excluded. A questionnaire was used to collect their biodata, the study included both males and females who were 18 years old and above. The weight was recorded in kilograms to the nearest 0.1 kg using a weighing scale, and the height was recorded in meters to the nearest 0.05 m. The body mass index (BMI) was calculated as the weight in kilograms divided by the square of the height in meters, according to WHO guideline [16]. Hypertension was a systolic blood pressure of ≥ 140 mmHg or a diastolic blood of ≥ 90 mmHg on at least two occasions (according to ACC/AHA hypertension guidelines) [17], or if the patient was on antihypertensive drugs. It also included individuals who had hypertension or diabetes and were on antihypertensives and/or antidiabetic medication. Participants with a fasting blood sugar level from 100 to 125 mg/dL (5.6 to 6.9 mmol/L) is considered prediabetes. A blood glucose level of 126 mg/dL (7.0mmol/L) or higher after an eight-hour fast, or a non-fasting glucose level of 200 mg/dL (11.0mmol/L) or higher is within the diabetic range, IDF criteria [1]. Data analysis was performed using MS Excel 2016 and STATA version 15.0. Chi-square test was used to determine the association between Body Mass Index and sex and age group with level of significance set at $P < .05$.

Results

A total of 199 eligible subjects (63 males, 136 females) participated in this study. The mean age of the participants was 48.5 ± 14.33 years. The majority of the participants, 102 (51.3%) were aged 41-60 years. One hundred and thirty-six (68.34%) while sixty-three (31.66%) were males. The mean body mass index of the study participants was 26.22 ± 5.77 kg/m² while the mean systolic and diastolic blood pressures were 141.22 ± 24.74 and 84.22 ± 11.67 mmHg, respectively. The mean fasting blood sugar and random blood sugar were 6.15 ± 4.03 and 6.36 ± 2.55 mmol/L, respectively. The age-sex distribution and general characteristics are shown in Tables1 and 2.

Table 3 shows the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in this population to be approximately 6.5% (n=13) with male being 6 in number and female of 7 number. Participants within the age of 41-60 had are more in

number (7) followed by those >60 who are 5 in number, though majority of the population had normal fasting blood glucose. 13(6.53%) participants were pre-hypertensive while 43(21.61%) had normal BP. 143 (71.86%) of the participants were hypertensive with systolic BP above 130mmHg and diastolic BP of above 80mmHg. 77(38.69%) of the participants had normal weight with BMI between 18.5 Kg/m² and 24.9 Kg/m², 24(%) were underweight with BMI below 18.4 Kg/m², 49(24.62%) were overweight with elevated BMI between 25-29.9Kg/m² while a total of 49 were obese (Class 1, 17.09%, Class 2, 5.53% and Class 3, 2.01%) with BMI of above 30.0 Kg/m² (Table 2). Three subjects had FBG of above 6.1mmol/L, and one is a known diabetic on medications with controlled blood glucose (3.8mmol/L). The characteristics of the diabetic subjects are shown below in Table 5.

Table 6 shows that 13(6.52%) of the 199 participants in this study were known diabetics with 12 of them being on medication. Also, among the 175 persons who had normal results, 4 (2%) were known diabetics and had been on medication.

Figure 3: Sex Distribution of the Participants

Figure 4: Bar Chart Showing Age Distribution

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of Participants

	MALE (%)	FEMALE (%)	TOTAL (%)
18-40 years	23 (36.51)	32 (23.53)	55 (27.64)
41-60 years	24 (38.09)	78 (57.35)	102 (51.25)
>61	16 (25.40)	26 (19.12)	42 (21.11)
TOTAL	63 (100)	136 (100)	199 (100)

Table 2: General Characteristics of the Study Participants

Metrics	Value
Total Participants	199
Clinical variables	Mean ± SD
Age	48.5 ±14.33
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	
Systolic	141.22 ±24.74

Diastolic	84.22 ±11.67
Blood Sugar (mmol/L)	
Random blood sugar (RBG)	6.36 ±2.55
Fasting blood sugar (FBG)	6.15 ±4.03
BMI	26.22 ±5.77
BMI Grouping	
Underweight	24 (12.06%)
Normal	77 (38.69%)
Overweight	49 (24.62%)
Obese C1	34 (17.09%)
Obese C2	11 (5.53%)
Obese C3	4 (2.01%)

Table 3: Age- and Sex Adjusted Prevalence of DM and Pre-DM

	FASTING BLOOD GLUCOSE				P-value
	Normal (%)	Pre diabetic (%)	Diabetic (%)	Total	
SEX					0.145
Female	119 (59.80)	10 (5.01)	7 (3.52)	136(68.33)	
Male	56 (28.14)	1 (0.50)	6 (3.02)	63(31.66)	
Total	175 (87.94)	11 (5.53)	13 (6.53)	199 (100)	
AGE RANGE					0.148
18 – 40 years	53 (26.63)	1 (0.50)	1 (0.50)	55(27.63)	
41 – 60 years	87 (43.72)	8 (4.02)	7 (3.52)	102 (51.26)	
>60 years	35 (17.59)	2 (1.01)	5 (2.51)	42(21.11)	
Total	175 (87.94)	11 (5.53)	13 (6.53)	199 (100)	

Table 4: Age, Sex and BMI Characteristics of Patients Detected to be Diabetic

S/N	AGE	SEX	FBG	BMI	BMI GROUP
1	62	F	17	32.9	OBESE C1
2	65	M	9.1	25.9	OVERWEIGHT
3	48	F	13.3	27.8	OVERWEIGHT
4	53	M	12.1	22.2	NORMAL
5	67	F	7.8	25.9	OVERWEIGHT
6	62	F	7	21.2	NORMAL
7	56	M	16	21.8	NORMAL
8	50	F	29	29	OVERWEIGHT
9	53	F	8.1	28.5	OVERWEIGHT
10	78	F	7.9	21.6	NORMAL
11	34	M	16.2	15.6	UNDERWEIGHT
12	53	M	20.8	17.8	UNDERWEIGHT
13	54	M	11.1	22.2	NORMAL

Table 5: Sex- and Age-adjusted prevalence of the diabetic population

	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
18 – 40	1 (7.69)	0 (0)	1 (7.69)
41 – 60	4 (30.77)	3 (23.08)	7 (53.85)
>60	1 (7.69)	4 (30.77)	5 (38.46)
Total	6 (46.15)	7 (53.85)	13 (100)

Note: Total diabetic = 13

Table 6: Showing the Previously Known Diabetics and Those on Medication

FBG	PREVIOUSLY KNOWN DIABETIC	ON MEDICATION
Normal (n=175)	4 (2%)	4 (2%)
Diabetic (n=13)	7 (3.52%)	7 (3.52%)
TOTAL	11 (5.52%)	11 (5.52%)

Figure 5: Bar Chart Distribution of FBG

Discussion

In this population, the prevalence of diabetes was 6.5% and that of pre-diabetes was 5.53%. Diabetes is also more prevalent in people aged 41 year and older

without a statistically significant relationship. The high prevalence shown in this study may be explained due to modernization, which has been affected by an increase in petroleum exploration and sedentary lifestyles.

The prevalence of diabetes in this study is higher than the prevalence of 6.2% found among 7663 urban residents and the 2.5% prevalence found among 7805 rural residents in populations of five West African countries [18], and 6.1% globally [19]; but, lower than the prevalence of 9.8% for south-south[8], prevalence of 9.0% reported among 600 residents in Ekpoma, Edo State, south-south geopolitical zone in [20] and the previous prevalence rate of 6.8% in Port Harcourt [13]. Also, this prevalence is considerably higher than the prevalence of 2% among 199 residents in a northern Nigerian suburban population [11]. The finding of such a high prevalence in the South-South region is worrisome and suggests that this could be as result of dietary and lifestyle differences between the two regions. Diabetes and lifestyle modifications have been linked, as seen in Mauritius, where 10.4% of Creoles had type 2 diabetes [21]. It has been observed among Nigerians that living in an urban area, not exercising, growing older, and eating a poor diet were the main risk factors for DM [8]. Research has shown that the number of urban dwellers in sub-Saharan Africa is changing at one of the fastest annual rates in the world [18]. Research has also indicated that living in an urban area is associated with a two- to five-fold increased incidence of diabetes and pre-diabetes [22,23]. Reduced physical activity energy expenditure, an independent risk factor for metabolic syndrome, is similarly linked to urbanization [24].

A vast majority (68.34%) of the study population are female. This could be because women think more about their wellbeing than men. Men tend to be more focused on trying to cater for the need of their family. Majority (87.94%) of participants had normal FBG, 5.53% were pre-diabetic while 6.53% were diabetic. A slight majority (54%) of the participants detected to be diabetic are female and above 40 years of age (Tables 3, 4, 5), though our analysis did not show a statistically significant influence of age and gender on diabetes. The result of this study is similar to the general global pattern of higher prevalence among the females [19] but in contrast the global pattern as at 2004, where it was found that diabetes was more prevalent in males than females. In this study only one subject with diabetes was below 40 years. Generally, prevalence of diabetes increases with age in both males and female up to around 65-70 years when prevalence in females overshoots that in males [3].

Of the 13 (6.53%) diabetic people in this study, majority of them were aged 41 – 60 years and >60 year (Table 3). The population of Port Harcourt is aging as a result

of the relatively small increase in living standards that has been observed over the last few years, which is due to the industrial and commercial activities brought about by the availability of petroleum in this region. As people age, they typically experience worsening insulin resistance [25], this raises the risk of type 2 diabetes together with age-related declines in physical activity. Unhealthy eating habits were the most common risk factor for diabetes mellitus (DM) [8]. This is not surprising given the widespread presence of fast food restaurants in many areas across Port Harcourt. Obesity and diabetes mellitus are largely caused by a poor diet heavy in energy-dense, high-fat foods.

The development of type 2 diabetes mellitus is predicted to shift to younger people due to a high rate of migration of younger adults to urban regions in quest of higher education and jobs [26,27] and significantly greater behavioral risks for type 2 DM in urban settings [28]. Also, living in an urban area such as Rumuomasi, exposes people to a variety of additional psychological stressors, including poverty, poor housing, pollution, competition, and overcrowding. These factors can raise the risk of non-communicable diseases, such as hypertension and type 2 diabetes [18,29,40]. Research has shown that blood pressure tends to rise more quickly under stressful settings and can be linked to changes in metabolism and physiology [30], aiding in the explanation why hypertension is more common in urban people than in rural areas [18]. It was observed in this study that participants with hypertension were found to be more likely to have type 2 DM than those with normal blood pressure, underscoring the significance of managing hypertension in reducing the prevalence of type 2 DM. This observation is consistent with previous studies conducted among Sub-Sahara Africa, Chinese and Indian populations [27,30,30-32].

In the general participant, majority (38.69%) had normal BMI, 24.62% were overweight, 17.09% were class 1 obese, 5.53% class 2 obese while just 2.01% were class 3 obese. This figure for overweight is comparable to that reported by another research, 21%, 21.4% [11,33]. As also shown in prior local studies [34,35], there was a low prevalence of obesity in this sample. Although obesity is a major risk factor for pre-diabetes and diabetes, especially in industrialized nations, it was surprising to find that very few of those who are diabetic and pre-diabetic are obese. This could be explained by the considerably high levels of physical activity observed among the participants.

Only one (8%) of the diabetics (n=13) was obese (Class 1) with BMI of 32.9Kg/m² and very high FBG of 17mmol/L, (Table 4) this is similar to a study in Northern Nigeria [11]. Three (3) persons were underweight, the rest were either overweight or normal weight. This shows that being overweight is enough modifiable risk factor for type for type 2

diabetes not necessarily obesity. The increased prevalence of obesity and diabetes in third world countries like Nigeria is said to be influenced by the "westernized diet" that is becoming more and more popular in African environments. This diet consists primarily of highly refined carbohydrates with high sugar and fat content, leading to being overweight. Excess weight which is not managed leads to obesity. Because obesity results in insulin resistance and β cell dysfunction, it is a key risk factor for pre-diabetes and type 2 diabetes, especially when it is accompanied by increased intra-abdominal and abdominal fat distribution as well as increased intrahepatic and intramuscular triglyceride content [36-39].

Considering pre-diabetics, the prevalence is 5.5% among the study population. This is considerably lower than the prevalence of 21.5 % found among 824 residents in a rural community in Enugu State, South-East, Nigeria [34]. A great majority of the pre-diabetic subjects were females, also majority of the pre-diabetics are between the ages of 41 and 60 years (table 3, 4).

13(6.52%) of the 199 participants in this study were previously known diabetics (table 4) with 12 of them being on medication. Also, among the 175 persons who had normal results, 4 (2%) were known diabetics and had been on medication. This shows that diabetes medication is effective in controlling blood glucose level and people with diabetics should be encouraged to adhere to medications. This study shows that 53.85% of the diabetic population were previously known to have diabetes while the remaining 46.15% were newly diagnosed. This number is slightly lower than that found by a previous study in Port Harcourt where there were 58.8% of people previously known to have diabetes among diabetic population [13]. The difference observed may be related to increases awareness on the issue of diabetes. This calls for more awareness for people to take their blood glucose level serious.

Conclusion

The prevalence of diabetes in Port Harcourt is relatively high compared to other regions of Nigeria. This could be explained by the changing lifestyle brought on by industrialization and westernization. Older age adults are more at risk of developing diabetes due to the years they have spent on unhealthy lifestyle. Enlightenment campaigns on routine glucose checks, campaigns highlighting the value of a traditional lifestyle, particularly with regard to diet should be carried out more often by the government and other stakeholders.

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